

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 16: Configuring the Objective Space Manager

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Abstract

This tutorial demonstrates how to configure the objective space manager to define various normalization strategies in the evolutionary multi-objective optimizers.

Keywords: JECDM, EA, evolutionary algorithm, normalization

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1. Introduction

This tutorial document demonstrates how to configure the *ObjectiveSpaceManger* to customize the normalization process. This class is responsible for

1. updating the knowledge on the relevant objective space bounds; it is done in the default extensions of *AbstractPhaseEA* just after the initial population or the offspring is constructed, evaluated, and assigned IDs;
2. notifying other interested components about the potential change in the possessed knowledge about these bounds;

Note that “objective space” is here a general term and does not mean that the manager intends to uncover the whole feasible bounds on objectives. Instead, it can be configured to serve various needs, e.g., understanding the span of the Pareto front. Also, note that the interested components mentioned in (2) are pre-defined in the algorithm configurations (e.g., NSGA-II [1]). By default, upon being notified, these components construct suitable normalization functions that map the objective vectors being examined into $[0, 1]^M$ hypercube, where M denotes

the number of objectives, 0 is a utopia point being considered the best, and 1 is the nadir point being considered the worst. For instance, NSGA-II uses these functions to calculate proper crowding-distance values.

This tutorial presents how to configure the manager to serve various needs. It provides two sources. The first demonstrates the configuration of the NSGA-II algorithm, while the latter concerns a preference-learning IEMO/D method. The latter case imposes greater challenges in terms of designing an efficient optimizer.

2. Customizing the normalization process in NSGA-II [T]

Source package:
`t11_t20.t16_customizing_normalization.Tutorial1`

This tutorial concerns running NSGA-II on the standard 2-dimensional DTLZ2 problem. Please examine the source code for details. The script presets 7 sub-scenarios – cases. These are presented in what follows. Note that the code is already well-commented. Thus, the descriptions in this document are relatively brief. Note that the code prints the current data on the known relevant objective space bounds after executing the last generation of the method.

Case #1:. This straightforward case assumes pre-fixing the OS manager data using $[0, 1]^2$ bounds. Listing 1 presents the relevant source code, while Figure 1 presents the expected console output.

Listing 1: Case #1

```
// CASE 1: This scenario assumes fixed data  
on the relevant (e.g., Pareto)  
objective space bounds.
```

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```

// The utopia and nadir points are set to
// [0.0, 0.0] and [1.0, 1.0]. Note that
// when both points are provided,
// the initial and fixed ObjectiveSpace
// object will be instantiated and coupled
// with the ObjectiveSpaceManager.
// Otherwise, the objective space will be
// considered null.
5 /*{
   b.setFixedOSBoundsLearningPolicy(
       dtlzBundle._normalizations, dtlzBundle
       ._utopia, dtlzBundle._nadir);
   }*/
}

```

```

Utopia point = 0.000007704382630 0.000036988101308
Nadir point = 1.030467387212091 1.076695232065945
Ranges data:
Left = 0.000007704382630; Right = 1.030467387212091
Left = 0.000036988101308; Right = 1.076695232065945
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Process finished with exit code 0

```

Figure 2: Console output (case #2)

```

Utopia point = 0.000000000000000 0.000000000000000
Nadir point = 1.000000000000000 1.000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = 0.000000000000000; Right = 1.000000000000000
Left = 0.000000000000000; Right = 1.000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Process finished with exit code 0

```

Figure 1: Console output (case #1)

Case #2:. This case assumes pre-fixing the OS manager so that it will learn dynamically the relevant bounds in the objective space using the current population and offspring specimens. The manager is set not to retain any memory of past data. Listing 2 presents the relevant source code, while Figure 2 presents the expected console output.

Listing 2: Case #2

```

// CASE 2: This case assumes dynamically
// learning the objective space bounds
// without any initial data.
5 /*{
   b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy();
   }*/ // CASE 2: This case assumes
// dynamically learning the objective space
// bounds without any initial data.
/*{
   b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy();
   }*/
}

```

Case #3:. This case assumes dynamically learning the relevant bounds in the objective space. Additionally, the initial utopia and nadir point is supplied, and the information on the utopia is retained from one iteration to another. Listing 3 presents the relevant source code, while Figure 3 presents the expected console output.

Listing 3: Case #3

```

// CASE 3: This case assumes dynamic
// learning with utopia and nadir points
// provided. As with CASE 1,
// the provision of both will ensure the
// creation of an initial ObjectiveSpace
// object with these two points.
// While the initial utopia is set to [0.0,
// 0.0], the nadir is set to an infinite
// vector. Nonetheless, it will
// be quickly updated just after creating
// and evaluating the initial population (
// see the following code):
5 /*{
   b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy(null,
       new double[]{0.0d, 0.0d},
       new double[]{Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY,
           Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY});
   // By using a dedicated adjuster, we
   // may further customize the objective
   // space manager maintained by the
   // algorithm:
   b.setOSMPParamsAdjuster(p -> {
       // we will assume that in each
       // iteration the data on the utopia
       // point will be updated using the
       // additional incumbent point; i.e.,
       // the method will maintain a utopia
       // consisting of the best objective
       // values found so far; since the
       // initial point is set to [0.0,
       // 0.0], which is also a true utopia
       // for
       // DTLZ2, no further change is
       // expected in this regard:
       p._updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent = true;
       // In contrast, we will not use a
       // nadir incumbent. It means that, by
       // default, the nadir will always be
       // determined using the current
       // population and offspring:
       p._updateNadirUsingIncumbent = false;
   });
   }*/
}

```

```

Utopia point = 0.000000000000000 0.000000000000000
Nadir point = 1.047806528206978 1.043989096628309
Ranges data:
Left = 0.000000000000000; Right = 1.047806528206978
Left = 0.000000000000000; Right = 1.043989096628309
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Process finished with exit code 0

```

Figure 3: Console output (case #3)

Case #4:. This case assumes dynamically learning the relevant bounds in the objective space. Additionally, the initial utopia and nadir point is supplied, and the information on the nadir is retained from one iteration to another. Listing 4 presents the relevant source code, while Figure 4 presents the expected console output.

Listing 4: Case #4

```

// CASE 4: Similar case to CASE 3, but uses
// opposite assumptions regarding the
// utopia and nadir. Thus, nadir is
// not expected to change in this example (
// but could, if some solution would exceed
// its coordinates), but the
// nadir will always be determined based on
// the current population and offspring:
/*{
5   b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy(null,
//      new double[]{0.0d, 0.0d},
//      new double[]{10.0d, 10.0d});
10  b.setOSMPParamsAdjuster(p -> {
//      p._updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent = false
//      ;
//      p._updateNadirUsing
//      Incumbent = true;
15  });
}*/
}

```

```

Utopia point = 0.000056115260320 0.000000093002001
Nadir point = 10.000000000000000 10.000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = 0.000056115260320; Right = 10.000000000000000
Left = 0.000000093002001; Right = 10.000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Process finished with exit code 0

```

Figure 4: Console output (case #4)

Case #5:. This case extends the previous ones by showcasing how to provide a custom listener that will be triggered when

the manager detects a change in the known relevant bounds of the objective space. Listing 5 presents the relevant source code, while Figures 5 and 6 present an example notification printed by the custom listener and the expected final console output.

Listing 5: Case #5

```

// CASE 5: This case assumes providing
// initial utopia and nadir and using their
// incumbents. Note that the
// initial utopia is set to [0.2, 0.2]. It
// means that there is some space left for
// improvement. The following
// code additionally notifies (prints to
// console) when there was an update in the
// data on the objective space
// in the most recent generation.
/*{
5   b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy(null,
//      new double[]{0.2d, 0.2d},
//      new double[]{1.0d, 1.0d});
10  b.setOSMPParamsAdjuster(p -> {
//      p._updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent = true;
//      p._updateNadirUsingIncumbent = true;
//      // We will add an additional-to-the-
//      // method-specific OS-changed listener
//      // to the manager. These listeners
//      // are triggered when there is an
//      // update on the known data in the
//      // relevant part of the objective space
//      :
15  p._listeners = new IOSChangeListener[]{
//      (ea, os, prevOS) ->
//      System.out.println("Data on the PF
//      bounds updated in " + ea.
//      getCurrentGeneration() + "
//      generation")
20  };});
}*/
}

```

Case #6:. This case extends the previous ones by showcasing how to provide custom specimen providers to the manager. They can serve, e.g., as external archives. Listing 6 presents the relevant source code, while Figure 7 presents the expected console output.

Listing 6: Case #6

```

// CASE 6: The last case showcases that the
// OSManager has the potential to be
// coupled with an external archive.
// The example assumes dynamic learning
// without any initial data. Also, using
// incumbents is disabled. However,
// the code specifies "specimen getters"
// that serve as data providers when
// OSManager starts processing. The
// PopulationGetter and OffspringGetter are
// regular (default) getters that request
// the manager to examine the

```

```

Data on the PF bounds updated in 0 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 1 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 2 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 3 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 4 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 5 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 7 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 9 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 16 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 19 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 20 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 25 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 26 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 109 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 111 generation

```

Figure 5: Console output (case #5, 1)

```

Data on the PF bounds updated in 0 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 1 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 2 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 3 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 4 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 5 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 7 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 9 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 16 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 19 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 20 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 25 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 26 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 109 generation
Data on the PF bounds updated in 111 generation

```

Figure 6: Console output (case #5, 2)

```

5 // Pareto front bounds using the current
  population and offspring. This code,
  however, adds a custom provider
// that delivers two pre-fixed dummy
  performance vectors [0.0, 0.0] and [5.0,
  5.0]. Since the first point
// cannot be improved and the second
  worsened (in the assumed problem
  definition), they will effectively serve
// as a pre-fixed utopia and nadir.
/*{
10 b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy();
  b.setOSMPParamsAdjuster(p -> {
    p._updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent = false;
    p._updateNadirUsingIncumbent = false;
    p._specimenGetters = new

```

```

15     ISpecimenGetter[] {
      new PopulationGetter(),
      new OffspringGetter(),
      container -> {
        ArrayList<Specimen> specimen =
          new ArrayList<>();
        specimen.add(new Specimen(new
          double[]{0.0d, 0.0d}));
20        specimen.add(new Specimen(new
          double[]{5.0d, 5.0d}));
        return specimen;
      }
    }
  };
  });
25 }*/
}

```

```

Utopia point = 0.0000000000000000 0.0000000000000000
Nadir point = 5.0000000000000000 5.0000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = 0.0000000000000000; Right = 5.0000000000000000
Left = 0.0000000000000000; Right = 5.0000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Process finished with exit code 0

```

Figure 7: Console output (case #6)

Case #7: By default, a *StandardLinearBuilder* is used when deriving normalization functions from updated data in the objective space. The construction process is triggered by method-specific objective space changed listeners. This builder maps the relevant part of the objective space into $[0, 1]^M$ hypercube, where M denotes the number of objectives, 0 is a utopia point being considered the best, and 1 is the nadir point being considered the worst. Various rescaling-dependent components, e.g., the crowding-distance measure, execute rescaling of specimens' performance vectors before making the calculations. Nonetheless, there is a possibility of changing the builder, if needed. In this example, a custom builder is set. It prints the input data on the objective space but ignores it when constructing the normalization functions. The latter are assumed pre-fixed. Listing 7 presents the relevant source code, while Figure 9 presents an example console output triggered during the detection of the change in the relevant objective space bounds.

Listing 7: Case #7

```

// CASE 7: This case assumes dynamically
  learning the objective space bounds
  without any initial data.
/*{
  b.setDynamicOSBoundsLearningPolicy();
  b.setNSGAIIParamsAdjuster(p -> p.
    _normalizationBuilder = OS -> {
5     System.out.println("Objective space is
      ...");

```

```

System.out.println(OS);
INormalization[] normalizations = new
    INormalization[]{
        new Linear(0.0d, 1.0d),
        new Linear(0.0d, 2.0d)
    };
System.out.println("But the
    normalizations are...");
for (INormalization n : normalizations)
    System.out.println(n);
return normalizations;
});
}*/
}

```

```

Objective space is...
Utopia point = 0.0000 0.0000
Nadir point = 1.1455 1.2417
Ranges data:
Left = 0.0000; Right = 1.1455
Left = 0.0000; Right = 1.2417
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
But the normalizations are...
Linear normalization: min = 0.000000; max = 1.000000
Linear normalization: min = 0.000000; max = 2.000000

```

Figure 8: Console output (case #7)

Figure 9: Final expected render

References

- [1] Deb, K., Pratap, A., Agarwal, S., Meyarivan, T., 2000. A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 6, 182–197. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/4235.996017>.
- [2] Tomczyk, M.K., Kadziński, M., 2020. Decomposition-based interactive evolutionary algorithm for multiple objective optimization. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 24, 320–334. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2019.2915767>.

3. Customizing the normalization process in preference-learning MOEA/D [T]

Source package:
t11_t20.t16_customizing_normalization.Tutorial2

This tutorial focuses on customizing the learning process of the relevant objective space bounds in preference-learning evolutionary methods for multi-objective optimization. It is much more challenging than for regular *a posteriori* methods, e.g., NSGA-II, due to the existence of a feedback loop between the optimizer and the preference-learning algorithm. Specifically, a change in the bounds on the optimizer part may trigger re-learning preferences, which in turn may re-adjust the convergence process, which may again trigger re-learning, and so on. It may not only be computationally inefficient but also may lead to ill results. The source code, which is not discussed here for the sake of convenience, is well-described and demonstrates a simple yet effective strategy that alleviates this problem. Figure 9 illustrates an example final render, where the preference-learning IEMO/D [2] was able to learn the decision-maker’s preferences and adjust the search correctly.